

Legal Certainty Of Credit Agreement After Credit Restructuration By Businessmen That Affected By Covid-19

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 11, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Legal Certainty, Credit Agreement, Restructuration, Businessmen, Covid-19.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5090711</p>	<p><i>The Indonesian economy has weakened due to the Covid-19 outbreak. In practice, to develop a business, businessmen need large funds for that, so not a few businessmen need credit agreements. But with the Covid-19, new problems arise, namely non-performing loan or bad credit. So the bank do credit rescue by means of credit restructuration. The concrete purpose of a credit resuce is to save the bnk as creditor and businessmen as debtor. Therefore, this research was conducted to determine the existence of the initial agreement after the rescue of credit in the form of credit restructuration and whether the creditors and debtors have received their rights and obligations equally. This reserach is a normative juriical research with data from from primary and secondary elgal materaials as well as cases related to bad credit due to Covid-19. Results of research indicate that the legal force of the credit agreement after the credit restructuration could not be said to be fully strong. Due to there are still differences in the regulations of each creditor. Between debtors and creditors have not received equal legal protection.</i></p>

Introduction

The Indonesian economy has weakened due to the Corona Virus Disease 2019 outbreak or often referred to as COVID-19. The virus caused the economy to be temporarily stopped and even totally stopped. One of the reasons is that businessmen do not have a lace to run their business due to everything is limited. Other than that there is also the idea to break the chain of virus by making everyone to stay at home, so that there is no economic movement from small business actors or other businessmen. Whereas the econom is the most important part in human life, which humans could not be separated from their economic life due to their position as social beings.

In practice, not a few of businessmen who starting or developing their business require large funds for capita and additional capital. What could be done by businessmen is to ask for credit in the bank to require their needs. Due to bank is a financial institution whose business activities are in the form of collecting public funds and then channeling them back in the form of credit.

In terms of language, credit agreement has the meaning of trust, which means taht the creditor has trust in their debtors to provide credit and at the agreed time it wil be returned. In short, credit in a broad sense is based on the components of trust, risk anf future economic exchange. The real meaning is that the occurrence of a credit agreement is determined by the delivery of money by the bank or creditor to the customer or debtor.

Starting from mid-2020, the problem that often arises in the conomy is bad loans due to the impact of COVID-19. This happens due to the income is not as it should be, so that businessmen who are also creditors have difficulty paying installments to the bank. Both large businesses and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME). Even though MSME in developing countries are quite influential, which their contribution to the formation and growth of gross domestic product (GDP) is larger compared to the contribution of large businesses.

This pandemic makes some things that happen not according to what has been agreed. Such as a change in the time of payment, the amount of the amount paid every month or installments and the end of the installment payment. Not a few of businessmen who change the type of business they do. This is done so that they could maintain their business in this pandemic situation.

So that automatically Covid-19 makes the income of businessmen unstable and must aply for waivers in credit payments or loan payments extensions to ease loans. Even though the State has issued countercyclical regulations through the Financial Services Authoirty, in a credit agreement it ust also be considered so as not to harm creditors and debtors.

Every agreement must pay attention to both parties and must benefit both parties at the same time. These things must be considered in mkaing changes to the loan system at the Bank as previously mentioned. Based on the background above, this article examines the first problem, how is the srength of the initial credit agreement after

the change in the loan system? Secondly, how is the legal protection for creditors and debtors after the regulations regarding credit loan relief?

METHODS

This research uses normative juridical research. The problem approach used in this research is the Statue Approach, which this approach is carried out by examining all laws and regulations related to the said legal issues. Johny Ibrahim stated that “Normative juridical research could and must utilize the results of empirical scientific research but these empirical sciences is considered as auxiliary sciences (*hulm wetenschap*) so that they do not change the nature of legal science as normative science.” The data collection technique used is a literature research centered on the law governing credit agreements and banking law.

DISCUSSION

1. Legal Force of Credit Agreement After Credit Relaxation of Businessmen that Affected by COVID-19

The COVID-19 pandemic affected various sectors, therefore it needs several ways to maintain a business. In addition to that, many businesses stopped due to this pandemic. Whereas in running a business, these businessmen have to pay monthly installments for loans at the bank.

The provision of credit by the bank must measure the level of risk of the factors that cause credit loans to default. This risk is estimated using a process called credit analysis. The main purpose of credit analysis is to determine the ability and sincerity of the debtor in accordance with the requirements contained in the loan agreement. The definition of bad credit is credit that could not be repaid either partially or completely due to something that is difficult or could be overcome by the debtor.

In practice, not a few experienced objections in paying bank installments. So what could be done is to apply for credit relaxation or often also called credit restructuring. The credit restructuring is one of the bank's efforts to do credit settlement.

One of the objectives of the debt restructuring is to target micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) who are the most impacted part of society due to the pandemic. According to OJK rules Number 11/POJK.03/2020 regarding National Economic Stimulus as a Countercyclical Policy for the Impact of the Corona Virus Disease 2019 outbreak, it is explained that debtors who receive special treatment in this POJK are debtors including MSME debtors who have difficulty fulfilling obligations to the Bank due to debtors or the debtor's business is affected by the spread of COVID-19, either directly or indirectly.

Prior to the credit restructuring, creditors and debtors had made an initial credit agreement according to the proper regulations. Then after this pandemic made changes to these credit payments. One example of the change is that the monthly installment of Rp. 1,400,000 (one million four hundred) per month should not be paid for up to 3 (three) months, so that you could apply for credit relaxation.

Starting with application to the bank to apply for credit relaxation or credit restructuring, then the bank as the creditor will conduct review of the business by the businessmen or debtor. If all requirements are met for relaxation, it could be approved by the bank.

But the question among common people is what is the fate of the existing credit agreement? Is it enough just to have a letter of agreement between the parties? Or will the initial credit agreement be deleted and replaced by a new credit agreement? These questions are confusing among the people. Due to there are differences in the regulations of several credit providers or creditors.

If viewed from the side of agreement law, between the debtor and creditor has created a debt and credit relationship, which the debtor has obligations to repay the loan that has been given by the bank, with the terms, periods, conditions, and agreement that has been accepted by both parties. With the agreement also gave birth to the rights and obligations between each party.

In practice, creditors or financial service institutions have their own additional regulations regarding the restructuring or relaxation of these loans. This happens due to there are creditors who must continue to get results from the credit. So it is still considered to be just looking for profit. For example, there are differences in the form of granting credit relaxation between Bank A and Bank B. Bank A uses relaxation approval letter and does not change the initial credit agreement and which only pays interest for installment payments. Meanwhile, Bank B settles non-performing loans with credit novation or debt renewal, which will automatically erase the old agreement.

By only observing the two examples above it can be certain that between creditors and debtors there is no balance in obtaining legal protection in the event of a case like the current one. Legal protection for debtors and creditors is very important in the settlement of non-performing loans. Due to both are interrelated and have their respective rights and obligations so it will be difficult if one of them feels harmed.

2. Legal Protection for Creditors and Debtors After The Regulation Regarding Credit Loan Relief

Through the regulation of POJK Number 11/POJK.03/2020 regarding the National Economic Stimulus as a Countercyclical Policy for the Impact of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 outbreak (COVID-19), customers could apply for credit restructuring through various ways such as deferral of payment to reducing interest payments and principal debt. The restructuring agreement was carried out by considering the willingness of two parties,

namely debtors and financial service institutions such as banks and financial companies. However, the restructuring is not enough to solve the problems that occur.

Restructuring is carried out by the Bank as an effort in a forced condition. For example, a business whose 60% is funded by the bank and the remaining 40% is the debtor's capital. Then when an obstacle arises where the debtor could not run his business, thus the customer is unable to pay the principal and/or interest.

This happens due to the different regulation of each creditor or bank. According to creditors, the regulation was formed to facilitate solving existing bad credit problems, which in practice creditors also need creditors also need the benefit of monthly installment payments, as creditors feel entitled to make regulation that are considered to be able to settle the problems faced by debtors and creditors themselves.

With these regulations, when we viewed from the debtor side who have difficulty to repay credit installments every month, there are pros and cons in it. As debtor has obligations to comply with the applicable regulations or terms and conditions from the creditor as agreed. But not a few of debtors also object to the existence of these regulations. This should be considered due to the rights and obligations of both parties in the credit agreement must be mutually complied with. And everything that happens must be based on agreement.

Legal protection that could be obtained by the creditor in terms of the settlement of bad credit are as follows:

1. Creditors could do selection in advance towards the debtors that fulfilled the criteria for being affected by COVID-19 (Article 2 (1) POJK Number 11/POJKL.03/2020 regarding National Economic Stimulus as a Countercyclical Policy for the Impact of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 outbreak;
2. An agreement with the debtor about the non-performing loans will be settled by restructuring or financing (Article 2 paragraph 2 POJK Number 11/POJK.03/2020);
3. Make regulations for credit rescue.

Legal protection that could be obtained by the debtors in terms of the settlement of bad credit are as follows:

1. Legal certainty in the agreement. In practice, there are objections to credit agreement who made by only one party. As a debtor, you do not know the content and terms of the standard agreement made by the creditor. In addition, the debtor is also less aware of the legal consequences. Thus it could be concluded that the debtor is forced to sign the agreement. The reason for this existence of a standard agreement is for the sake of efficiency. One form of legal certainty is the fulfillment of the legal requirements of the agreement, in Article 1320 to Article 1338 of the Civil Code. It is true that the agreement exists with the approval of the agreement clause by both parties, but in this case, one of the parties, namely the debtor, must accept it due to circumstances. Thus the debtor must obey or be subject to the terms and conditions set by the bank or creditor;
2. The agreement is formulated in clear and easy to understand sentences. As well as providing sufficient opportunity for the debtor to understand the contents of the agreement made by the creditor. This is one to meet the criteria in the Consumer Protection Law;
3. For businessmen, especially micro, small and medium enterprises, Law Number 20 Year 2008 regarding Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises should discuss the settlement of non-performing loans, so that the debtors get legal protection as they should be.

The World Bank provides advice regarding economy policy to overcome the impact of Covid-19, namely:

That countries need to take an integrated and intertemporal view of health, containment, and macroeconomic policies, rather than see them as separate instruments to achieve separate goals. Therefore, creditors and debtors should decide on a win-win solution due to the initial agreement they made was based on an agreement. There must be clarity if there is a change in the clause in the agreement and unexpected things occur, such as the current pandemic or *force majeure*.

CONCLUSION

The legal force of credit agreement after the credit relaxation of businessmen that affected by COVID-19 could not be said to be strong. Due to there are still differences in the regulations of each creditor. Thus making debtors and creditors to be not equal in obtaining legal protection. Legal protection for creditors is to be able to select debtors who will be given relief and make regulation regarding credit relaxation for debtors. Meanwhile the legal protection that must be obtained by the debtor after the regulation regarding credit loan relief is legal certainty in the agreement as well as knowing and full understanding the content of the agreement. In this case, the government should have clear regulation and legal certainty regarding the settlement of bad credit in this pandemic. So there is no overlapping of regulations. The firmness of the government is needed to form creditor in order to meet the criteria as have been set. Generalize the regulation regarding credit relaxation in the event of pandemic situation like in the present days.

In addition, debtors and creditors must get legal protection so that they could create a win-win solution between the two parties. By still paying into consideration of the rights and obligations of both parties. In addition, sanctions for debtors who are late in paying their installments, better to have sanctions for creditors or banks if they could not comply with the existing regulations.

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